

MnFeNiGeSi High-Entropy Alloy candidate with Large Magnetocaloric Effect

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Abstract: The magnetocaloric effect of high-entropy alloys (HEAs) due to a second-order phase transition exhibits limited response. $\text{Mn}_{22.3}\text{Fe}_{22.2}\text{Ni}_{22.2}\text{Ge}_{16.65}\text{Si}_{16.65}$, with the entropy of mixing of a HEA presents a significant improvement as it exhibits a magneto-structural first-order phase transition. Its isothermal entropy change of $7.3 \text{ J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ (for 2.5 T) is the largest reported to date for rare earth-free HEAs. The alloy composition was found by a directed search that starts from a low entropy alloy with the desired transformation combined with isostructural substitutions. Although $\Delta S_{\text{mix}} = 1.60 \text{ R}$, the enthalpy of mixing approaches to, but does not reach, the HEA criterion. Our findings demonstrate the potential of finding HEA with magneto-structural phase transition and with promising potential as high-performance magnetocaloric materials.

Keywords: High-entropy alloys; First-order phase transition; Magneto-structural transformations; Functional properties; Magnetocaloric effect

Introduction

One of the most relevant recent changes of paradigm in materials science and, certainly, the most important in the field of metallurgy and alloy development, is the concept of High-Entropy Alloys (HEAs), by which the central region of multielement phase diagrams is explored. HEAs comprise of multiple principal elements to form a “baseless” alloy without single dominant element, unlike the traditional way of designing alloys (i.e. alloying to one main constituent). Its design can allow several elements to be substituted on a single sublattice while maintaining the host structure despite elements of different crystal structures in their elemental forms are incorporated in the alloy [1]. This characteristic of having more principal elements than sublattices is a possible way to expand the possibilities of identifying new functional materials. Other than the large compositional freedom, HEA design concept has led to transformative opportunities for developing advanced alloys, especially for finding outstanding properties for structural applications with phase stability and improved wear and corrosion resistance as these properties could, overall, improve service-life, efficiency and effectiveness of the component used during applications. This presents many opportunities for HEAs to overcome the bottlenecks of conventional materials if HEAs with the appropriate functionality are found, however reports on their functional properties are still underway and reported values are modest unlike for their structural studies and mechanical properties [2-7]. Although there have been numerous attempts to find outstanding magnetic properties of HEAs including density functional theory, the enormous compositional search space to be rationally explored is a notable challenge. Moreover, functional properties at room temperature cannot be easily predicted by ab-initio models, motivating the disappointing lack of correlation between predicted properties and those actually measured values. Brute force solving the problem was a feasible solution for binary or ternary systems in the previous centuries but it is impossible with materials consisting of five or more elements that can be varied.

Magnetocaloric HEAs known to date exhibit second-order thermomagnetic phase transitions (SOPT), which are broadened due to the distributed exchange interactions that arise from the disorder[8] and motivating their modest responses when compared to top performing magnetocaloric materials[9]. They could be enhanced by using rare-earths (RE) as reported for $Gd_{20}Dy_{20}Er_{20}Ho_{20}Tb_{20}$ HEA [10]. For transition metal HEAs, the way to improve the magnetocaloric effect (MCE) should be to incorporate a first-order phase transition (FOPT). For that purpose, deviation from the strictly equi-atomic compositions of Cantor alloy is needed [11].

In this work, we aim to realize FOPT in HEA by starting with a medium-entropy alloy (MEA) composition, MnNiSi, which undergoes a structural transformation from hexagonal to orthorhombic phase [12, 13]. Considering appropriate isostructural substitutions, we

formulate a RE-free quinary HEA candidate system of nominal composition $\text{Mn}_{22.3}\text{Fe}_{22.2}\text{Ni}_{22.2}\text{Ge}_{16.65}\text{Si}_{16.65}$ where a large MCE of $7.3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for a field of 2.5 T is found, in a temperature range that would be suitable for natural gas liquefaction applications.

Materials and methods

The considerations for selecting the composition were: (i) starting composition should exhibit the behavior sought for, (ii) choice of doping element(s) should be chemically compatible for isostructural substitutions and (iii) stoichiometry of the element plus the substitutions should be maintained. We started with MnNiSi, which undergoes a structural transformation from hexagonal to orthorhombic at 1200 K upon cooling [12, 13]. By appropriate isostructural substitutions, we select Fe and Ge. The content of these elements is tuned towards the goal of an entropy of a large entropy of mixing (ΔS_{mix}) of 1.60 R, corresponding to a HEA, and formulated a RE-free HEA quinary $\text{Mn}_{22.3}\text{Fe}_{22.2}\text{Ni}_{22.2}\text{Ge}_{16.65}\text{Si}_{16.65}$. We also characterized the broadly accepted additional empirical parameters of HEA design criteria of atomic size difference (δ), enthalpy of mixing (ΔH_{mix}) and Ω , a thermodynamic parameter correlating ΔH_{mix} and ΔS_{mix} (calculations were based on refs. [5, 14-17]). The values of these magnitudes for the starting and new alloys, together with the accepted requirements for HEAs [7, 14, 18] are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Empirical parameters for HEA design, including the starting alloy, the new alloy and the requirements for obtaining a HEA.

Magnitude	Starting alloy (MnNiSi)	New HEA ($\text{Mn}_{22.3}\text{Fe}_{22.2}\text{Ni}_{22.2}\text{Ge}_{16.65}\text{Si}_{16.65}$)	Requirements for HEAs [5, 17]
δ (%)	2.4	3.3	≤ 6.4
ΔS_{mix} ($\text{Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)	1.10 R	1.60 R	$1.5 \text{ R} \leq \Delta S_{mix} \leq 1.61 \text{ R}$ (for quinary alloy)
ΔH_{mix} (kJmol^{-1})	-26.22	-14.9	$-15 \leq \Delta H_{mix} \leq 5$
Ω	0.573	1.43	≥ 1.1

It is shown that both ΔS_{mix} and δ fulfil the requirements for being considered a HEA, while (ΔH_{mix}) and, consequently, Ω , fall outside the desired range. In **Figure 1**, ΔS_{mix} is plotted

against δ , presenting the classification of different alloy types (low-, medium- and high-entropy alloys) according to their ΔS_{mix} values (the defined threshold of ΔS_{mix} for the different alloys are based on [5,17]). The yellow region in **Figure 1** marks the parameters widely accepted for predicting the phase formation in HEAs. For HEAs containing significant amounts of non-transition metals, the criteria become more stringent ($\delta < 4.5$ %), which is presented as the blue area. The formulated $\text{Mn}_{22.3}\text{Fe}_{22.2}\text{Ni}_{22.2}\text{Ge}_{16.65}\text{Si}_{16.65}$ for this work (represented as a sphere) falls in the zone classified for HEAs, even inside the restricted region for those containing non-transition metals, while MnNiSi (open crossed circle symbol) lies in the MEA region.

Figure 1. Plot of ΔS_{mix} versus δ of the alloys from ref.[41] (calculations based on refs. [15, 17]).

The alloy was prepared by arc melting pure elements (purity higher than 99.9 wt.%) in an argon atmosphere. The ingot was flipped and melted four times for homogeneity. The bulk chemical composition of the alloy was characterized through its cross-section using scanning electron microscope equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX; FEI™ Teneo). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded at the BL02B2 beamline of SPring-8, using a wavelength of 0.6199 Å and MYTHEN detector

[21]. Temperature control was performed using a N₂ blower, and the magnetic field was applied with permanent magnets.

MCE was indirectly determined, via Maxwell relation, from isothermal magnetic measurements up to 2.5 T performed in a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer by recording isothermal magnetization (M) vs magnetic field (H) curves in a discontinuous protocol [22] that erases the memory of the sample between measurements, thus avoiding spurious results regardless of the order of the thermomagnetic phase transition [22, 23].

The magnetic field dependence of ΔS_{iso} adopts a power law expression [24]:

$$\Delta S_{iso} \propto H^n, \quad (1)$$

with an exponent n , both field and temperature dependent, that can be locally calculated as:

$$n = \frac{d \ln |\Delta S_{iso}|}{d \ln |H|}. \quad (2)$$

Curves were rescaled using the universal curve method [24] with a reference temperature, T_r , that fulfils $\Delta S_{iso}(T_r) = 0.6 |\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}(H)|$.

The temperature averaged entropy change, $TEC(10)$ [25], consists in the maximum average of the ΔS_{iso} over a 10 K temperature span and was defined as alternate figure of merit of magnetocaloric materials to avoid the artificially large refrigerant capacity of shallow peaks. For its calculation from literature data without digitizing the whole curves, we have approximated it as:

$$TEC(10) = \frac{1}{10} \max \left(\int_{T-5}^{T+5} \Delta S_{iso}(T') dT' \right) \approx \frac{\Delta S_{iso}(T_{pk-5}) + \Delta S_{iso}(T_{pk}) + \Delta S_{iso}(T_{pk+5})}{3}. \quad (3)$$

Results and Discussion

Temperature dependent magnetization

Figure 2 shows the thermomagnetic curves for Mn_{22.3}Fe_{22.2}Ni_{22.2}Ge_{16.65}Si_{16.65} measured after the virgin curve where three distinct regions as marked by the dashed lines can be observed: low ($T < 125$ K), intermediate ($125 < T < 170$ K), and high temperatures ($T > 170$ K). For $T > 170$ K, magnetization gradually decreases with increasing temperature for all magnetic fields, suggesting SOPT ferromagnetic to paramagnetic (FM-PM) transition, which is similar to the magnetocaloric HEA reported in the literature. For intermediate temperatures, abrupt magnetization changes are observed, especially for 130–140 K and

156–166 K. For low H (gray region), magnetization increases upon heating as the low temperature phase transforms into a phase of higher magnetization, which can be similar to a metamagnetic transition. Conversely for $H > 0.5$ T, the alloy transforms from a higher magnetization phase to a lower magnetization phase upon heating. Although hysteretic, both transitions are reversible. For $T < 125$ K, magnetization increases with H as expected.

Figure 2. Thermomagnetic curves of MST-HEA measured at 2 K min^{-1} for various magnetic fields after virgin effects.

Microstructural characterization

A single hcp phase structure is found in room temperature XRD characterization (**Figure 3(a)**). Elemental maps acquired from SEM-EDX reveal no element-rich regions although two phases are found. The main phase composition corresponds to the nominal one; the minority phase is Si-depleted and has typical size of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$. The detection of single phase from the XRD results could probably be because the two regions observed from SEM-EDX are both hexagonal with similar lattice parameters. Both phases fulfill the criteria for HEA design as listed in **Table 1**: $\Delta S_{\text{mix}} = 1.59 \text{ R}$ for the main phase; for the minority Si-depleted region, $\Delta S_{\text{mix}} = 1.56 \text{ R}$. The ΔH_{mix} value lower than the usual range for single phase HEA agrees with the existence of the two phases. Furthermore, it has been reported that HEAs can exhibit secondary phases in TEM

observations though both XRD and neutron diffraction results indicate that the alloy consists of a simple FCC solid solution phase [42].

Figure 3. (a) Room temperature XRD (Cu K α) shows only $P6_3/mmc$ phase while SEM-EDX (inset) shows a majority of $Mn_{23.2}Fe_{22.9}Ni_{22.9}Ge_{14.7}Si_{16.3}$ with minority Si-depleted regions of $Mn_{27.3}Fe_{17.9}Ni_{23.0}Ge_{21.4}Si_{10.4}$. Temperature dependence XRD measured in temperature interval of 10 K for cooling (b) and heating modes (c) show the desired structural transformation.

The temperature dependence of synchrotron-XRD (**Figures 3(b)** and **(c)**) reveals the phase transformation of hexagonal $P6_3/mmc \leftrightarrow$ orthorhombic $Pnma$, whose crystallographic structural transition is similar to that of the starting MEA $MnNiSi$ [12, 13]. This suggests that Fe and Ge doping could act as solute atoms in the solid solution, retaining the host structures of the starting MEA considered for our search approach. A mixture of $P6_3/mmc$ and $Pnma$ coexisting for ~ 130 – 170 K and at low temperatures are observed while no more $Pnma$ are detected above 190 K. The temperature region of mixed phases is in agreement to the intermediate temperature region of the thermomagnetic results, which indicates that the abrupt magnetization changes observed in **Figure 2** are attributed to the phase transformation of $P6_3/mmc \leftrightarrow Pnma$. Hence, the thermomagnetic results show $Pnma$ phase at low temperatures which then transforms into $P6_3/mmc$ phase at higher temperatures. The presence of $P6_3/mmc$ phase detected at low temperatures (**Figure 3(b)** and **(c)**) was due to the inhibition of full transformation induced from grinding the sample for the preparation for XRD measurements [26]. We can, therefore, denote our sample as MST-HEA from this point onwards.

The temperature dependence of synchrotron-XRD for an applied field of 0.5 T (**Figure 4(a)**) displays the same crystallographic structural transition of orthorhombic \leftrightarrow hexagonal phase upon heating as observed in **Figure 3**. However, evident texture effects are noticed for the peaks at $2\theta \sim 16.5$ and 19.1° due to powder alignment with H . Both

peaks are less resolved though we can still observe them at the same Bragg peak positions. **Figure 4(b)** shows increased intensity of the diffraction peak corresponding to 020 reflection of low temperature *Pnma* phase upon cooling, where the peak intensities were normalized at the lowest temperature.

Figure 4. (a) Temperature dependence XRD of MST-HEA with 0.5 T applied field. (b) Normalized diffraction peak intensity from the 020 reflection of the *Pnma* phase.

Functional property characterization – MCE

MST can give rise to relevant caloric effects, being MCE one of them. **Figure 5(a)** shows ΔS_{iso} of MST-HEA. The high temperature FM-PM transition leads to a direct MCE (negative ΔS_{iso}), which is the SOPT-type usually observed for the magnetocaloric HEAs in the literature [10, 27-31]. For the region of MST, two types of MCE are observed at $T \sim 143$ K: inverse MCE (positive ΔS_{iso}) for $H < 0.50$ T, which transforms to direct MCE for higher H .

There are two methods that use MCE analysis to identify for FOPT: its fingerprint via the quantitative criterion based on MCE [32]; and (lack of) universal scaling of MCE [24]. For the former, we use that the magnetic field dependence of $|\Delta S_{iso}|$ follows a power law of the field (**equations 1 and 2**) whose exponent n has been recently found showing an

overshoot of $n > 2$ near the transition temperatures for FOPT [32]. The latter is based on the assumption that only SOPT scale onto a universal curve. **Figures 5(b)** and **(c)** show the exponent n and rescaling of MCE data (considering only the MST region) for MST-HEA, respectively. An overshoot of $n > 2$ coinciding with the temperature at which MST occurs indicates that MST-HEA undergoes a FOPT in that range. Exponent n decreases immediately after the overshoot due to transiting to the FM state of the subsequent FM-PM transition of hexagonal phase at high temperatures. A minimum n is observed at the temperature of the peak of high temperature direct MCE (T_{pk}), indicating the SOPT character of the Curie transition. Hence, the subsequent increase in exponent n observed for higher temperatures is expected as the typical SOPT asymptotically tends to $n = 2$ in the PM state. On the other hand, the rescaled MCE of MST-HEA in the temperature region where MST occurs does not collapse onto a universal curve as shown in **Figure 5(c)**. This indicates that the MST is of FOPT-type, which agrees with results from the exponent n behavior.

Figure 5. (a) $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ for various magnetic fields (measured in cooling mode). The first-order MST evidenced by the fingerprint of field dependence exponent n and by (b) poor collapse of normalized MCE data vs. rescaled temperature, which deviates from a universal curve.

Figure 6 shows the isothermal hysteresis loops (only first quadrant is shown, including the initial magnetization curve and the demagnetization) which show a large effective anisotropy field of ~ 0.6 T at low temperatures (orthorhombic phase) that reduces to ~ 0.08 T at higher temperatures (hexagonal phase). This is due to the decrease of symmetry in the lattice that increases the anisotropy. A small difference in the initial magnetization curve and the loop is noticed up to 1.5 T for 140–147 K. Coercivity is negligible for all cases. The observed behavior regarding the change of anisotropy is similar to that of Ni_2MnGa -based conventional functional materials [33-35]. For low

fields ($H < 0.27$ T), magnetization increases with temperatures, which attributes to the observed inverse MCE in **Figure 5(a)**. For higher fields ($H > 0.27$ T), magnetization decreases with increasing temperatures, which leads to the direct MCE observed for high fields in **Figure 5(a)**.

Figure 6. First quadrant of the isothermal hysteresis loops including initial magnetization curve and demagnetization measured in cooling mode which show two different anisotropy fields at low ($T \leq 136$ K) and high temperatures ($T \geq 150$ K).

Figure 7 shows that the MCE performance (based on peak values of isothermal entropy change, $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}|$, at its corresponding temperature T_{pk} , and temperature averaged entropy change, TEC) of MST-HEA demonstrates a significant improvement in comparison to reported magnetocaloric HEAs, with a $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}| \sim 2.9$ times larger and an increase of TEC of $\sim 86\%$ when compared to the largest MCE of RE-free HEA [28]. As for RE-containing families, MST-HEA shows from 38 to 175% and 10.6 to 89.4% increase for $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}|$ and TEC , respectively. This significant enhancement arises from the MST, which undergoes a FOPT. When comparing with the Gd-based melt-extracted microwires (also promising for nitrogen liquefaction application), our results imply an increase of 100% in $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}|$ and 34% in $TEC(10)$ [36].

Figure 7. MCE performance for magnetocaloric HEA for 2.5 T: $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}|$ vs. T_{pk} . Literature data collected from [10, 27-29, 31, 37-40]). Each data point represents a single material, with a diameter size proportional to its $TEC(10)$.

Conclusion

The first magneto-structural HEA, free from rare earths in its composition, provides an improvement of the $|\Delta S_{iso}^{pk}|$ of HEAs by 152-1500% when compared to transition metal HEAs (38-175% increase when including rare-earths in the comparison). The temperature range of the new alloy is suitable for natural gas liquefaction and compositional tuning is expected to adjust the transition temperature close to other operational ranges. These results clearly validate our goals of: (i) intentional designing HEA with MST phenomenon to boost its functional properties, MCE in this case, as compared to those obtained in conventional HEA systems, as well as (ii) premeditated searching for the MST-HEA composition starting from a MEA composition which is known to exhibit similar properties sought for. Our approach not only considers the rightful stoichiometry and element dopant of chemical compatibility but also considers appropriate isostructural substitutions for designing the composition.

Our findings can aid the community, both experimentalists and theoreticians, in their compositional search in the laboratories and/or in theoretical computational approaches, tackling the large compositional space allowed by HEAs. Hence, identifying

low or medium entropy alloys with specific functionalities and tuning their compositions towards the HEA concept is an important research goal for the future.

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Declaration of interest statement

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jia Yan Law: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing - original draft. **Luis M. Moreno-Ramírez:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Alvaro Díaz-García:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Andres Martín-Cid:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Shintaro Kobayashi:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Shogo Kawaguchi:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Tetsuya Nakamura:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Victorino Franco:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition.

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